

A Strong Start for Rubin Observatory Data Previews

Kristen Metzger
(AURA/Rubin Observatory)

In 2021 Vera C. Rubin Observatory began Data Preview Zero (DP0), the first of three data previews leading up to the start of Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). In its first few months, DP0 has proven successful with regard to its primary goals: 1) to train the operations team and test the functionality of Rubin's developing data infrastructure in the operations context; and 2) to introduce a diverse group of scientists to the tools and interfaces they'll use to access and analyze Rubin data. Community feedback obtained during DP0 is being used to guide the continued development of Rubin's data infrastructure and support materials.

Rubin Observatory is committed to research inclusivity, and one of the highest priorities for DP0 was to ensure that the DP0 participants, referred to as delegates, represent the full range of diversity in the science community. The call for delegate applications was broadly advertised, and the Rubin Observatory Community Engagement Team (CET) worked with Rubin leadership to identify and reach out directly to individuals at small or under-resourced institutions. The initial selection process, in May 2021, relied on an algorithm designed to prioritize participation from scientists and students who are under-represented in astronomy and to build a network of delegates from a variety of global locations, institutional types, career stages, and astronomical fields. The first couple of months of DP0 went so well that by November 2021 all the applicants were invited to become DP0 delegates, and an additional limited number of invitations have now been extended to delegates' students as well.

The several hundred delegates have now spent a few months using the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) to access simulated data products that are similar to those that will be produced during the LSST. Frossie Economou, who leads the development of the RSP, notes that the developers are gratified to see astronomers using the products they've been working on ahead of Rubin Observatory's first light. *"This first cohort of external users is a great opportunity for us to test our ideas out in the wild,"* notes Frossie. *"We have had internal RSP users for quite some time now, but there was always the possibility that in-project users were suffering from some form of Stockholm Syndrome. But more seriously, it's great for our developers to start settling into the mixed development-operations mode that will be the norm during the LSST campaign. While it is a challenge to balance the two with so much construction work remaining, there is great satisfaction in remembering the point of all this, and we can't wait for our own telescope's data to start flowing."* In addition to exploring new query, visualization, and analysis tools in the RSP, delegates are also learning to use the Rubin Observatory [Community Forum](#) to get help from their peers and colleagues. The Forum is intended to provide a sustainable support model where publicly shared ideas and solutions benefit the whole science community. The Rubin CET has also provided an extensive suite of [documentation, tutorials, and other resources](#) for delegates and has hosted online information sessions and delegate assemblies. In September 2021 the CET invited DP0 delegates to provide feedback about their experiences using the initial support resources provided by the CET. Overall, the survey results were extremely positive, and most respondents affirmed that the Community Forum and other core DP0 support resources

were serving them well. DPO Delegate Kristen Larsen, associate professor of astronomy and physics at Western Washington University, credits the CET and the support they've provided for her positive experience with DPO, adding, *"I feel much more confident and enthusiastic about jumping in to use real Rubin Observatory data when they arrive."*

The first few months of DPO have gone so well that Rubin Observatory leadership plans to allocate 300 new RSP accounts in the second phase of DPO, bringing the total number of DPO delegates to 600 by 30 June 2022. *"Our goal is to scale up sustainably,"* says Melissa Graham, Lead Community Scientist for Rubin Observatory, *"so we can protect our still-developing infrastructure and continue to provide adequate support for all delegates."* This deliberate and incremental growth will continue through the data preview process, and all Rubin data rights holders will be able to obtain RSP accounts by the time science operations begin. Meanwhile, DPO delegates are playing an important role in

building and strengthening the community of scientists using Rubin data for their research. Delegate Louise Edwards, assistant professor of physics at California Polytechnic State University, says DPO *"has motivated me to reach out to other LSST scientists, and I have been communicating regularly with folks at SLAC, NOIRLab, and across my university system about potential projects involving DPO data."*

The second phase of DPO is scheduled to begin on 30 June 2022. It will include a new dataset that has been reprocessed using a more recent version of the LSST Science Pipelines, and data products will be available in a format that is consistent with planned LSST data products. Additional data products, such as light curves, will also be available. The application form for new DPO delegates will open in early March and close on 30 April 2022. See [the Community Forum topic: Early announcement for Phase 2 of Data Preview 0 \(DP0.2\)](#) for more information about how to participate.

Vera C. Rubin Observatory with the southern Milky Way. Rubin Observatory is a joint initiative of the National Science Foundation (NSF) and the Department of Energy (DOE). Once completed, Rubin will be operated jointly by NSF's NOIRLab and DOE's SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory to carry out the Legacy Survey of Space and Time. *Credit: Rubin Observatory/NSF/AURA/B. Quint*